

Strengths and gaps for the market uptake of smart and flexible technologies for geothermal energy: outcomes from the Horizon 2020 GeoSmart Project

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ABSTRACT

The decarbonization of the energy sector sees an increase in fluctuating and non-programmable energy sources (wind and solar) and requires solutions to balance fluctuations that these may cause to electricity grids. On the other hand, geothermal is known for its reliability over time and the GeoSmart project (2019-2024, www.geosmartproject.eu) was aimed at demonstrating and optimizing innovative solutions to increase the flexibility of plants. These technologies were tested in two different sites: Kizildere II (Türkiye), which uses higher temperature and adopts the triple flash technology, and Insheim (Germany), an ORC plant using lower temperature resources. The project also investigated the opportunity to hybridize geothermal with other renewable energy sources to improve efficiency and flexibility. Geothermal resources can vary within a few kilometres and technologies should adapt to local conditions, making it challenging to standardize solutions. Case by case in-depth technical and economic analysis on feasibility is necessary to provide as many guarantees as possible to investors at their convenience. This work reports the main strengths and gaps identified for the replicability and market uptake of 1) silica retention system to decrease reinjection temperatures and prevent scaling, and high-temperature phase change material (PCM) energy storage, 2) low-temperature thermocline thermal energy storage with flexible ORC, and 3) geothermal flash plants hybridized with waste biomass and Parabolic Trough Collector (PTC). Geothermal flow assurance simulations have been performed, and an Open Access online simulation tool has been developed to further showcase these technologies in different operational environments and scenarios.

The GeoSmart project demonstrated solutions for flexible geothermal operation, but it is necessary to find solutions to improve the replication potential of these technologies, lower capital and operational costs and increase the technological maturity, particularly in the case of hybridization of geothermal power plants with CST (Concentrated Solar Thermal) and biomass. These gaps should be first overcome by continuing to support research and innovation for flexible geothermal solutions. This might concern support to further demonstrations in storage systems, to combine heat and power production in contexts with high temperatures and different plant layouts. In this framework, further research in geothermal hybrid solutions should also be supported, to increase their TRL (Technology Readiness Level) and be commercialized. Policies and measures to promote investments in renewable energy flexible solutions, as reported above, would result in their greater deployment, a decrease in equipment costs and more trust of investors in the long term.

1. INTRODUCTION

Future energy systems, thanks to progressive decarbonization, will be increasingly dominated by non-constant renewable sources, such as solar or wind, which by their nature will cause daily and seasonal fluctuations in the supply of electricity. To balance these fluctuations in production, it becomes necessary to use renewable sources with constant production over time, such as geothermal, as an ideal partner to random renewable sources, to increase the flexible response of the entire energy system. The GeoSmart project, funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 program, aimed to demonstrate the feasibility of innovative solutions to increase the flexibility of geothermal plants, through their implementation on plants already in operation. For this reason, it was considered to install a Silica Scaling Reduction System and a PCM Thermal Energy Storage on an existing high-enthalpy flash geothermal plant, the Kizildere II plant, operated by Zorlu Energy and located in Türkiye. These two systems can help to

optimize the energy exploitation of the geothermal fluid, increasing the overall production and efficiency of the plant, and to ensure a more flexible supply than conventional plants. As an alternative, it was decided to install a Flexible ORC and a Water Thermocline Thermal Energy Storage system on a medium-low enthalpy binary CHP plant, the Insheim plant (Germany) managed by Vulcan Energy. These systems can increase flexibility in energy production, so that electricity can be produced when heat demand is lower, and flexibility in energy supply, given by the thermal storage system. In addition, a simulation was carried out to determine the benefits and challenges posed by the hybridization of a geothermal plant with a biomass plant and a concentrated solar plant. For this part of the research, the Turkish geothermal plant of Kizildere II was chosen as a case study regarding the possibility of hybridization, due to the physical and economic characteristics of the territory in which it is located. This part of the research aimed to solve two common problems of geothermal plants, namely the energetic quality of the geothermal brine degrading over the years and the degraded performance of geothermal power plants during hot ambient temperature periods.

2. METHODS

Information reported in this article is the result of a literature review, benchmarking with results of existing techno-economic analysis on hybrid geothermal power plants and the collaboration efforts with all the partners of GeoSmart project. Regarding the solutions proposed by GeoSmart, it was decided to consider two cases: 1) Kizildere II, where the Silica Scaling Retention Tank and the PCM Thermal Energy Storage were installed; 2) Insheim, where the Flexible ORC and the Water Thermocline Thermal Energy Storage were installed. The project consortium decided to consider these technologies because they have the best replication potential, amongst the innovations proposed by GeoSmart. The Turkish plant of Kizildere II was chosen as a case study regarding the possibility of hybridization. The reference market description and analysis, including customers and competitors will refer to the Turkish framework (Çelebi, 2024). For this research, a market analysis was carried out both in the case of the individual technologies proposed and in the case study of the hybrid plant, identifying the main categories of target customers and carrying out a market analysis through a macroeconomic perspective, following criteria of a PESTEL analysis, which covers many prevailing market factors, as Political, Economic, Social, Technical, Environmental and Legal aspects (Fahey & Narayanan, 1986). Partners involved conducted desk research and gathered their internal information on PESTEL factors and identified barriers, threats and opportunities to the development and operation of proposed solutions. The competitive drivers and their impact have been analysed through Porter's five forces analysis (Porter, 1980 and 2008). A SWOT (abbreviation for Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats) analysis led to the identification of external and internal factors that help to identify the strategic planning of installing the

GeoSmart technologies or hybridizing the geothermal power plant. Finally, the replication potential for the technologies proposed by GeoSmart and for the case of hybridization of an existing plant was evaluated, highlighting through a Gap Analysis the main critical factors for installation in other plants.

2.1 The Silica Scaling Reduction System

Within the GeoSmart project, a silica scaling abatement system has been developed that uses a scaling reactor and a retention tank to drastically reduce the amount of amorphous silica in the geothermal fluid. This allows on the one hand to achieve lower reinjection temperatures (up to 50 °C) and on the other hand to double the amount of heat extracted from the fluid. It also allows the silica extracted from the fluid to be recovered later, which can be sold on the market. This system (Fig. 1) has been installed in Kizildere II plant and cools down 50 t/h of the geothermal fluid, from 104 to 50 °C, through a 3 MW heat exchanger. The system's design capitalizes on the dual mechanisms of molecular deposition and polymerization of monomeric silica. The cooling of the brine from 104 °C to 50 °C results in a silica supersaturation ratio of 2,46, given the initial concentration of 451 ppm SiO₂ and an equilibrium solubility of 183 ppm at 50 °C.

Key design features include:

- Induction pipe: prepares the brine via pH conditioning and seed introduction.
- Scaling reactor: maximizes surface-assisted deposition of silica.
- Retention tank: promotes laminar flow to favour homogeneous polymerization.

The 10,7 m³ scaling reactor and a 10 m³ retention tank, with a mass flow of 5 t/h, allow a retention time to be 128 minutes for the scaling reactor (silica deposition on plate surfaces) and 120 minutes in the retention tank (silica polymerization). The system efficiency (η_{RS}), defined as the fraction of silica removed compared to the required drop to reach saturation, is estimated at 69% under test conditions with 5 t/h mass flow. This implies an outlet silica concentration of ~265 ppm before reinjection, effectively mitigating scaling risks. Chemical additives are fundamental elements to guarantee the optimal required conditions (Taddei Pardelli et al. 2021). It is also possible to exploit the retention system with different plant setups depending on the characteristics of the system and the geothermal fluid involved. Furthermore, to enhance system durability and fouling resistance, various coatings were evaluated:

- Epoxy paints
- Fluoropolymer-based coatings
- Sol-gel amorphous materials

These coatings reduce the surface free energy, significantly lowering the adhesion of silica scales in aggressive geothermal environments.

Figure 1: Silica Scaling Reduction System design (Taddei Pardelli et al. 2021).

2.2 The PCM Thermal Energy Storage

The Phase Change Material (PCM) energy storage tank stores latent heat using a mixture of inorganic salts as PCM within a shell-and-tube heat exchanger. Heat transfer fluid flows through finned tubes, enhancing thermal exchange via an aluminum matrix (“Fiocco”). Nitrogen blankets the PCM and compensates for volume changes during charging (melting) and discharging (solidifying). The tank supports three modes: while charging the hot source fluid melts the PCM in the tank; during discharging the cold source fluid solidifies the PCM and goes out of the tank at a higher temperature. Between a charge and a discharge phase, the tank can remain in a static state (standby). This system, (Fig. 2), has been installed in the Kizildere II plant. In GeoSmart, a closed water loop exchanges heat with geothermal brine. The system allows efficient thermal storage, detailed in GeoSmart project Deliverable 2.2 – Energy storage system design schematics.

Figure 2: Phase Change Material Thermal Energy Storage (PCM-TES) (GeoSmart Project Deliverable 9.5)

2.3 The thermocline thermal energy storage

The Water Thermocline thermal energy storage has been installed in the Insheim plant. It can store sensible heat by creating a piston-like temperature gradient in the fluid inside a tank. It operates in charging, discharging, and standby modes. During charging, hot water enters from the top, pushing cold water down and out; during discharging, cold water enters from the bottom, pushing hot water up and out. Flow is managed to maintain thermocline stability (Fig. 3). In GeoSmart, a closed-loop water system exchanges heat with geothermal brine and air-cooled condensers via a

hybrid exchanger. More details are in GeoSmart Deliverable 2.2 - Energy storage system design schematics.

Figure 3: Water Thermocline Thermal Energy Storage (GeoSmart Project Deliverable 9.5).

2.4 The flexible ORC system

The flexible ORC system at the Insheim plant supplies heat to a district heating network based on demand and converts residual geothermal energy into electricity. Though initially planned with a hybrid cooling system, an adiabatic fogging system was tested instead due to permitting issues. The ORC uses isopentane in a closed cycle involving heating, vaporization, expansion through a turbine, condensation, and recirculation. Simulations modelled the system using EBSILON® software and showed good alignment with real data, confirming the model's accuracy in estimating performance under various conditions.

2.5 Geothermal flash plants hybridized with biomass and solar thermal energy

A geothermal power plant in mediterranean or mild and hot climate areas, like the Kızıldere II Geothermal Power Plant in Türkiye, loses efficiency below 70% of its nominal capacity in hotter months (Çelebi, 2024). A hybrid system integrating Concentrated Solar Thermal (CST) and biomass (olive residue) addresses this by providing seasonal flexibility. CST supports summer performance, while biomass compensates in winter (GeoSmart project Deliverable 8.4 - Future geothermal configuration report). A topping and bottoming cycle configuration utilise existing turbine excess capacity, adding up to 16 MWe. The topping cycle generates power and supplies heat to the bottoming cycle. Biomass ensures continuous operation, while CST contributes during daytime, optimizing plant efficiency.

3. STRENGTHS AND CHALLENGES FOR THE GEOSMART TECHNOLOGIES

The following chapters analyze the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats related to the installation of the four single GeoSmart technologies considered. A separate paragraph will consider the SWOT Factors regarding the case study for a three-way hybridized geothermal-CST-biomass plant.

3.1 Silica Scaling Retention Tank

The application of the Silica Scaling Reduction System can allow for about twice as much energy to be extracted from geothermal fluids under the same conditions, increasing the production and revenues of the plant. It also greatly reduces the problem due to scaling, increasing the productive life of the plant and decreasing the need for other scaling prevention treatments (brine clarification, acidification, etc.). The main negative factor of this system is the installation and maintenance costs, which raise the installation and operational costs of the system. Opportunities to be exploited are represented by the surplus energy produced by the fluid and selling potential of the recovered silica. The installation of the system also allows for less frequently scheduled maintenance of the system, and has a positive effect on job creation, as it requires manufacturers, installers and maintainers. However, it must be evaluated on a case-by-case basis whether the increase in the plant's revenue compensates for the maintenance cost of the Silica Scaling Reduction System. In addition, the costs and benefits of installing this system must be evaluated in relation to other competing scaling reduction technologies, which may be cheaper.

A techno-economic analysis of full-scale deployment at Kizildere II (total brine flow of 1.700 t/h) demonstrated that coupling this system with a 10,7 MW low-temperature ORC could yield:

- Recovery of 936 GWh/year thermal energy,
- 86,89 GWh/year of additional electricity,
- 1.799 tons/year of commercial-grade silica (~€ 90.000 revenue/year),
- A Net Present Value (NPV) exceeding € 63 million,
- A payback period of 7 years.

3.2 The PCM thermal energy storage

Latent heat storage technologies using mixtures of inorganic salts are technologically mature. They can be exploited in a modular manner and occupy a reasonable volume, since the storage density of PCMs is much higher than that of sensible heat storage technologies. They also feature faster charge/discharge cycles. However, these systems still have some flaws: the PCM tank must always be insulated to prevent heat loss, and therefore efficiency. In the case of PCM replacement, salts must be properly disposed of and not dispersed into the environment, although they generally need to be changed about every 20 years. The installation of these systems represents an increase in the overall cost

of the plant (greater complexity of the plant), also considering that filling the tank generally has a significant cost. For now, such systems must be very large to have a significant impact on the earnings of a large-scale geothermal plant. In general, this technology will contribute to the increase in efficiency of renewable plants and therefore will benefit from the opportunities provided by EU policies for innovation in the field of renewable energy (improvement of the system over time and lowering of costs). In the future, this will lead to the application of this technology in other fields. The technology that exploits the use of salts is currently the dominant one on the market, but it will have to compete with many other thermal energy storage technologies, which are currently under development. In addition, the system has to deal with two physical phenomena that develop over time (supercooling and phase segregation) and decrease the efficiency of heat transfer and therefore cause it to lose efficiency.

3.3 The thermocline thermal energy storage

The thermocline TES is a technology now widely present on the market with a high degree of maturity, also due to the relative simplicity of the systems and the low maintenance required. In many cases the cost of filling the tank is close to zero, when using water as a storage medium. In many cases these systems do not take up much volume, although they have often been used for limited energy storage. The installation of these systems can be higher than other comparable technologies, since there is generally a need for large volumes of water to store heat in order to make a significant contribution to a geothermal system (lower storage density compared to PCM-TES). In addition, the storage temperature is generally much lower (below 100°C), and this can affect its applicability; The flow conditions necessary to keep the thermocline in the tank (slow flow) must always be maintained. Heat loss from the tank must be prevented, as in the previous case, although in this case loss can also occur due to the temperature gradient of the medium. As in the case of the PCM TES, these systems are also subject to improvement over time, in terms of performance, cost and the application of different solid and liquid storage media. Several research projects concern the application of sensible heat storage systems in groundwater to increase the flexibility of energy networks. This storage technology is considered the simplest and cheapest, although in the future it will have to face competition from other technologies (e.g. based on PCM or other types of storage). These systems are generally characterized by long charge/discharge cycles, due to the need for the establishment of the thermocline (slow flow parallel to the longitudinal walls of the tank).

3.4 The flexible ORC system

Flexible ORC increases the efficiency of a Combined Heat and Power (CHP) geothermal plant that prioritizes heat production, so that it can produce electricity when district heating demand is low. This makes it possible

to optimize the use of the geothermal resource and increase the flexibility of the plant. This technology uses a smart management system recently patented by VITO (Flemish Institute for Technological Research) that balances the heat supply to the district heating, the use of TES system when electricity prices are low and the power production when these are high. On the other hand, the applicability of this solution is not always obvious and must be assessed on a case-by-case basis. For example, in the case of the Balmatt plant (Belgium) it was found that the temperature range of the deep carboniferous reservoir did not allow a high efficiency of the ORC. In addition, even in the face of the benefits in flexibility and energy supply, the installation and maintenance of the technology represent significant extra costs to be incurred by the operator. Regarding the opportunities that can be exploited, the ORC can benefit from technological improvements over time (e.g. new building materials, plant engineering and further development of the control algorithm) and from the support of innovation policies in the field of energy. The installation of the ORC can also produce new jobs at the local level, with positive effects on social acceptability. New applications are being sought for both the ORC and the control algorithm: in particular, the use of a similar domestic heating system at the level of entire buildings (and not single homes) seems promising, because the thermal mass of the buildings could accumulate part of the heat. Further developments in the control program will lead to an increasingly efficient use of energy, allowing the production of heat and energy to be flexibly balanced and the reinjection temperature of geothermal fluids increasingly decreasing. However, the technological maturity of this solution remains quite low now, and most plant operators can have access to other systems with the same purpose (although perhaps less efficient) but already established on the market. In addition, the systematic use of ORC is not yet allowed due to the lack of long-term monitoring data. Finally, in certain countries, especially small ones, this application is in competition with other uses of the subsoil (accumulation of gas or CO₂).

3.5 Geothermal plants hybridized with biomass and solar thermal energy

Hybrid systems have several advantages from a technological point of view. Combining geothermal energy with solar and biomass increases the installed capacity of the plant, especially during the hot summer periods, and the flexibility of production. Hybridization can also help lower installation costs, since different infrastructures can be shared by multiple production technologies. This produces more profit for the operator, even when energy prices are higher, while reducing greenhouse gas emissions. In addition, the installation of CST and biomass modules creates new jobs along the entire production chain (production, installation and maintenance). The use of waste products (such as residual olives) for energy production for industrial production processes and heat for heating & cooling also provides benefits to local communities, increasing the acceptability of the plant. Turkish

entities have legal advantages in acquiring property, and current laws allow capacity increases without further permits if nominal geothermal capacity exceeds actual capacity. One of the main costs in the production of a hybrid plant is the need to purchase and/or level large portions of land, which are necessary for CST production. From a social point of view, given Türkiye's limited experience with CST technology, there is a need for qualified training for plant technicians, and the solar plant itself may face opposition from local communities, due to the impact of CST panels on the landscape and wildlife. In addition, the use of the area required for the CST module is always in potential competition with agricultural land use. From a technological point of view, competition with other renewable energy plants (especially wind and hydropower) is increasing in the Turkish market. In addition, Turkish law does not currently allow for an increase in installed capacity with CST beyond the nominal limit. Regarding opportunities, Türkiye's growing energy demand is encouraging operators to increase the capacity of renewable plants, both by building new plants and hybridizing existing ones. The government supports flexibility through the balancing power market, which may promote hybrid plants. High inflation raises energy prices, boosting profits. From a technological point of view, there is a wide range of solutions that can be integrated to increase the capacity of geothermal plants. In fact, the Turkish territory allows the installation of solar systems, thanks to the high average radiation to which it is subject. The use of biomass in agricultural areas promotes the idea of a circular economy. In addition, the current law allows all the energy produced by a hybrid plant to be treated as geothermal, guaranteeing the operator greater profits. The main threats include high Turkish inflation, which raises energy prices and loan interest rates, as well as construction and O&M costs. Competition in the Turkish market is influencing renewable energy companies, which are trying to offer ever better rates. The technological readiness of CST plants in Türkiye is low, as there are no operational plants. The technological components for CST plants often have to be imported and workers often need specific training. For now, there are no hybrid plants in Türkiye, and for now there is no law regulating them. However, this type of project would need a preliminary impact assessment according to Turkish law, due to the adverse effects it could have. Among the major external negative factors, Türkiye's high inflation, even if the price of energy sales increases, also increases interest on loans and costs for construction and O&M. The Turkish market is becoming increasingly free from state control and competition is increasingly high among renewable energy companies trying to assert themselves in consumer preferences.

4. GEOTHERMAL FLOW ASSURANCE SIMULATIONS

Flow assurance simulations have proven to be a key technology to reduce costs and risks in the oil & gas sector. Taking advantage of this, a new flow assurance

simulation software targeting geothermal energy applications has been developed. It has many different features, including for example 1D multi-phase & multi-component pipe network flows, thermodynamics, geofluid models, corrosion, 3D multi-physics, and optimization. It is several different solvers, all of them based on conservation equations and discretized with the finite element method. For brine with tracking of silica concentration, the governing equations are:

$$\frac{A}{a^2} \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \dot{m}}{\partial x} = 0 \quad [1]$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{m}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial U \dot{m}}{\partial x} + A \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \rho g A \frac{\partial z}{\partial x} + \frac{f \dot{m} |\dot{m}|}{2 \rho D A} = 0 \quad [2]$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho C T A) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (C T \dot{m}) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k A \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) + \phi \quad [3]$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (c) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (c U) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(K_L \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} \right) - R \quad [4]$$

where c is the concentration of silica dissolved in the brine and K_L is the longitudinal dispersion coefficient (Aris-Taylor dispersion for laminar flows, Taylor dispersion for turbulent flows). During the GeoSmart project, new models for the silica scaling reduction system as well as both the thermocline and PCM thermal energy storages were developed. In addition, a new silica scaling model based on the polymerization reaction kinetics of aqueous silica (GeoSmart project Deliverable 4.1 - Modelling of silica scaling potential) was implemented (denoted as R in Equation [4]). The software was used for various simulations of the GeoSmart systems. An example of the temperature and silica concentration profiles along the heat exchanger and silica scaling reduction system are shown in Fig. 4a. A lower flow rate means longer residence time in the system, leading to more silica polymerization and reduced concentration of dissolved silica.

Making the scaling reactor and retention tank larger will lead to a larger degree of polymerization, thereby reducing levels of silica concentration in the brine, which then in turn can be reinjected at lower temperature without increasing scaling-related risks. However, larger scaling reactor and retention tank would also lead to larger costs. To find the optimal balance between system size and related costs and benefits, an optimization methodology was developed, which is based on an iterative procedure that uses Design-of-Experiments (DoE), meta-modelling with the Kriging method, and global optimization using Genetic Algorithms. The procedure is summarized in Fig. 4b.

Figure 4: a) Flow assurance simulation results of silica concentration and temperature along the scaling reduction system; b) Iterative parametric optimization method

The flow assurance simulator was also used to calculate the effects of using Thermal Energy Storage combined with end-user demand variation, for example district heating daily and seasonal variations. Both the thermocline and the PCM TES are modelled with 1D finite elements along its axis, making it possible to see the propagation of the temperature front inside the TES during charging/discharging (Fig. 5).

Figure 5: a) Thermocline front at different times during charging; b) thermocline front at different times during discharging

A simplified, easy-to-use, Open Access version of the software has been deployed on Flowphys simulation portal, www.simuport.com (Fig.6 and Fig. 7). Different template-based cases are available, for example a case with geothermal production/injection wells, an ORC, district heating, and a TES. This freely available online tool makes it easy to investigate effects of different flow rates, temperatures, pipe sizes, TES capacities, and more.

Figure 6: Input GUI for online flow assurance simulations of a schematic geothermal plant.

Figure 7: Online simulator results.

5. THE REPLICATION POTENTIAL AND THE GAPS OF THE GEOSMART FLEXIBLE TECHNOLOGIES

Attempts have been made to evaluate the possibility of installing the technologies proposed by GeoSmart at sites other than Insheim and Kizildere II (GeoSmart Project Deliverable 9.5). This confirmed that the geothermal sector is closely linked to the operating conditions and the characteristics of the available resource. Therefore, it is difficult in this sector to standardize a technological solution and its

implementation, and in any case a technical-economic assessment of feasibility is necessary, to guarantee investors the convenience of the intervention. As for the Silica Scaling Reduction System, the implementation would be rather simple in other plants, but in any case, the benefits must be weighed in relation to the higher maintenance costs, compared to the usual acidification of the fluid. Incorporating the PCM-Thermal Energy Storage in large scale geothermal plants (high temperature) would generally require larger units than the one installed to have notable effect on operations. Additional components may also be required, depending on the design and conditions in the plant, to be able to incorporate the PCM. This would lead to an increase in installation costs and the volume required for the equipment. Despite this, the PCM technology could help to support other renewable energies by providing flexibility to counteract intermittent sources such as wind and solar energy. This would be particularly beneficial if the storage unit could be large enough to accommodate peaks in use over a few days period, anticipated by weather forecasts. However, the storage should be quite large, to provide measurable support, since smaller scale solutions are generally connected to lower temperatures. Water Thermocline storage is a good solution for storing medium-low temperature fluids and can also be used to balance the heat demand in geothermal district heating networks (as in the case, for example, of the Belgian plant of Balmatt). This is a simple solution that can be replicated at many other sites, greatly increasing the reliability of the heat supply. Different considerations must be made for Flexible ORC, whose efficiency is very much linked to the temperature range of the resource and therefore is not always applicable. The replication of GeoSmart technical solutions should also be favoured by appropriate market conditions. The greater flexibility of the plants, favoured by various technological solutions, should be rewarded. Thanks to these technologies, the plants can work in partial load if necessary and in some cases modulate their output according to the demand of the network. Operators of flexible RES installations can therefore offer ancillary services to system operators and provide valuable short and long-term flexibility at regional and transborder level, a step between centralised and decentralised systems. In this regard, most balancing regimes and infrastructure planners rarely take the potential flexibility from these technologies into consideration, except for Germany (Fraunhofer IEG, 2022).

The technological solutions proposed by GeoSmart to hybridize geothermal plants with CST and biomass modules currently have a very low TRL and need to reach a technological maturity to be commercially viable. This applies to both technologies for individual production modules and infrastructure for hybrid production. Nevertheless, the addition of CST and biomass can lead to the optimization of the existing geothermal plant, shortening the payback period and increasing revenues. Future implementations of hybrid systems will need to consider the local availability of solar radiation and biomass. For example, the Kizildere

II site is subjected to an annual irradiation of 1.800 kWh/m², which is the minimum threshold for the construction of an economically viable solar plant in Türkiye; moreover, the area is agricultural and represents one of the major oil-producing areas, which guarantees a large amount of biomass. However, this simultaneous presence of geothermal, solar and biological resources is not found in many European regions, as in many cases there is an abundance of biomass, in various forms, but solar radiation is often too low, especially in northern European countries. However, emerging technologies, especially in the geothermal field, could allow resources to be exploited at greater depths in many parts of Europe, and this could make it possible to hybridize existing plants. The financing of geothermal projects usually requires tailor-made approaches in terms of support mechanisms and

financial instruments due to the geographical and technological non-homogeneity of the geothermal sector. Therefore, to reduce uncertainty about the cost of the project, support schemes put in place by individual states or by the European Union, which can use a part of its budget to finance member states' projects, can help. EU is a key resource in several geothermal heating projects. In some countries, this support also takes the form of risk guarantees for deep geothermal projects, which can contribute to greatly reducing the costs of financing. In other cases, some associations, such as the European Business Angels Network (<https://www.eban.org/>) can help develop the best startups on the scene to facilitate investment activities in their field of technological innovation and find investors for a better exploitation of GeoSmart results.

Figure 8: Gap analysis scheme for the GeoSmart flexible technologies (GeoSmart Project Deliverable 9.5).

6. CONCLUSIONS

The GeoSmart project developed technical solutions to extract more energy from geothermal fluids and to increase the flexibility of plants that produce electricity and heat in a combined manner. The project demonstrated the application of these solutions in two existing plants (Kizildere II and Insheim), which represent the two main technologies of geothermal plants, namely flash plants and ORC cycle plants. Project results show that these technologies can be exploited on a commercial scale, to make geothermal energy increasingly competitive with non-renewable alternatives (e.g. natural gas plants). These solutions, such as thermal storage to increase the flexibility of CHP plants, or hybridization of plants with other renewable energy sources, must be adapted to various real-world situations. Therefore, it is necessary to show investors the convenience of using these technologies in their plants, as well as to share the results obtained from the tests in the demo sites.

The main gaps identified by GeoSmart (in Fig. 8) should be overcome first and foremost by continuing to support technological research in the geothermal field and innovation on systems to increase the flexibility of

plants. In addition, policy measures to promote investments in the flexibility of renewable resources would help to increase the use of GeoSmart's technological solutions, decrease their costs and increase investor confidence in the long term.

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